

Symbiosis of smart objects across IoT environments

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Final symbloTe Virtual IoT Environment Implementation

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1 Executive Summary

The aim of Deliverable D2.5 is to document the final set of components and provided features implementing the symbloTe framework for virtualization of IoT platforms enabling semantic and syntactic interoperability within the Cloud (symbloTe Level-1 of Compliance). The components will be integrated into the third symbloTe software release (Release 3). The symbloTe project has a challenging task of providing a cooperation environment for IoT platforms, enabling them to interoperate, collaborate and share resources. The main features enabling Level-1 Compliance affect two domains, as defined in Deliverable D1.4 [14], Application Domain and Cloud Domain. The main features are as follows: access to platform resources through an open symbloTe-defined interface within the Cloud Domain, search for registered platform resources and IoT-related services within the symbloTe Core Services (placed at the Application Domain), and a complete solution for authentication and authorization.

We are using previous symbloTe deliverables, especially Deliverable D1.2 [1] and Deliverable D1.4 [14], as inputs for our work. The analyses of requirements, use-cases, system architecture and semantic data, have made a foundation for software development. The symbloTe architecture (see [1] , [14]) is defining various levels of integration with symbloTe services for platform providers. In the first release of the symbloTe software (February 2017) the goal was to implement and integrate the essential features for Level-1 Compliance, e.g., registration and update of IoT platforms and resources, handling search requests for resources, and access to virtualized resources listed in search results. In the second release (May 2017) we have added support for actuation as well as mechanisms for authentication and authorization based on the Attribute Based Access Control (ABAC). Release 3 builds upon the previous set of developed components and adds the following new features for Level-1 Compliance:

- wider utilization of semantic web technologies – solutions in Information Models handling, platforms and resources description, search querying
- upgrade and new features in security layer solutions
- ranking and filtering algorithms for search results
- support for evolving Information Models in every related part of the system
- new resources monitoring features

This document reports the final design of symbloTe software elements for Level-1 Compliance which contain components grouped in domains, defines a complete list of component features, as well as their interactions and communication interfaces. The main outcome of this Deliverable D2.5 is the source code and its documentation, published as an open source project in the GitHub service [15]. This document is an accompanying report documenting the software.

The complete list of components implemented for symbloTe Level-1 Compliance is as follows:

- Core Services layer:
 - *Core Interface* - defines a unique way of interaction for end users and third-party client applications
 - *Administration* - allows to register new symbloTe users and platforms
 - *Authentication and Authorization Manager (AAM)* –offers mechanism for the authentication and authorization of symbloTe entities/actors, this component

can act as Core AAM and Platform AAM (in Cloud Domain), depending on configuration

- *Registry* - handles registration of symbloTe resources in core layer
 - *Search* - allows client applications to search for resources registered in symbloTe
 - *Semantic Manager* - a specialized component to handle RDF translation and validation processes of the Core functionalities
 - *Core Resource Access Monitor* – acts as a proxy which redirects client applications to the actual resources offered by symbloTe-enabled platforms
 - *Core Resource Monitor* – which is monitoring the availability of registered resources to regularly update resource status
 - *Monitoring* - responsible for two tasks: monitoring the status of resources and monitoring the access to resources from applications/enablers
 - *Cloud-Core Interface* – a gateway from core services to supported symbloTe-enabled IoT platforms
- Cloud Domain (IoT platform related part of the system):
 - *Interworking Interface* - gateway for communication of symbloTe platform-related components with the external world, replaced by NGINX server in last release
 - *Registration Handler* - allows an IoT platform to register and update its resources with symbloTe Core Services
 - *Resource Access Proxy* - enables symbloTe-compliant access to resources within an IoT Platform

Since Release 2 (21/05/2017) we also maintain a *symbloTeLibraries* repository, which is a set of common models, definitions and methods used in other components, in both layers mentioned above.

As of July 14th, 2017, we can report the following IoT platforms as being symbloTe L1 compliant:

- OpenIoT (<http://www.openiot.eu/>)
- Symphony (<http://www.nextworks.it/en/products/brands/symphony>)
- openUwedat (under development in AIT <https://www.ait.ac.at/>)

and work on intergration next plattforms is in progress.

symbloTe resources in GitHub service [15] contain descriptions and configuration guides for Core and Platform-side services and also explanations of the process on how to make an IoT platform symbloTe L1 compliant (placed as readme part in repository: <https://github.com/symbiote-h2020/SymbioteCloud>).

2 Introduction

Deliverable D2.5 provides a description of the final set of components and associated features implementing the symbloTe framework for virtualization of IoT platforms enabling semantic and syntactic interoperability within the Cloud (Level-1 Compliance). The total of 12 components have been implemented and integrated. Further, an additional component is used, a third-party component (NGINX). A common library of elements used in other parts of the system (both layers: Core Services and Cloud Domain) named *symbloTeLibraries* is developed and maintained.

Current document describes the basis of the design decisions, including the ideas that are supporting symbloTe software design and covering the topic of current state of the implementation. The existing outcomes from other symbloTe's workpackages (WP1 definition of requirements and architecture, WP2 Task 2.1 works on semantics) gave us a foundation for implementation of the symbloTe software components, so we are also shortly summarizing their outcomes.

The document is structured as follows: Chapter 3 contains a short summary of symbloTe reports used as guidelines for the current software implementation. Our goal is to document briefly the progress from requirements, through architecture definition, to design decisions in the implementation phase. Chapter 4 contains description of the existing components, the current state of component's features, and a list of usage scenarios supported. The main outcome of Task 2.2 is the symbloTe software, published on the project's GitHub repository [15].

The repository contains the source code of all implemented components, their Javadoc documentation, configurations and guidelines for software installation, setup and usage. In this context, Chapter 0 is a short, tabular overview of the existing L1 components and refers to the GitHub resources (appropriate links are included in tables).

GitHub resources includes also additional services, that are not mentioned in main set of symbloTe L1 Compliant components. For example, there are repositories like:

- demo web application which was used to showcase symbloTe ideas (<https://github.com/symbiote-h2020/Demo>)
- configuration (e.g. CoreConfigService, CloudConfigService) or supporting modules like Eureka, Zipkin

To avoid confusion please remember that *SymbloTeCore* and *SymbloTeCloud* repositories always contain information how to setup Core services layer (*SymbloTeCore*) and how to integrate an IoT platform with symbloTe (*SymbloTeCloud*). Current (and other) report can be outdated in some point of the future. In such a case, descriptions and guides included in README of the symbloTe GitHub repositories [15] should provide better, more up to date information about symbloTe system configuration and integration.

It is also important to mention, that symbloTe consortium will also prepare a separate deliverable, entitled "D5.2 – Report on System Integration and Application Development", which will be dedicated to the integration issues and should be taken under consideration by platform owners/developers, integrators and also developers who would wish to extend symbloTe Core Services.

3 Preliminaries

The main goal of symbloTe is to foster a simplified IoT application and service development process over interworking IoT platforms. In order to achieve this goal a set of software components, creating symbloTe system were developed and this chapter covers the most important assumptions, analyses, works, decisions and data models that drove this process.

3.1 Requirements and use-case analysis

To achieve the project goals the first steps were taken in WP1, initial analysis of requirements and use cases was performed. Over 80 requirements were recognized initially (the number fluctuated during the progress of the analysis) in which currently 49 are related to L1 related part of the system (4 in this are non-functional and also related to other levels of compliance). 5 practical symbloTe use cases were also recognized and analysed in the initial project phase. For further details in terms of use cases and requirements please refer to D1.1 [2], D1.2 [1] and D1.4 [14] respectively.

After the definition of system requirements, the symbloTe consortium has defined the initial functional architecture of the system in D1.2 [1], which is a direct foundation for software implementation reported in current deliverable and is extended in the final report D1.4 [14]. Current D2.5 document comes as a compound of D2.2 [5] and aforementioned deliverables.

3.2 symbloTe architecture

As it was already stated in detail in the symbloTe's reports on system architecture [1], [14], the symbloTe approach is built around a layered IoT stack connecting various devices (sensors, actuators and IoT gateways) within Smart Spaces with the Cloud. Smart Spaces share the available local resources (connectivity, computing and storage), while platform services running in the Cloud enable IoT Platform Federations and open up the Interworking Interface to third parties. The architecture comprises four layered domains, as depicted in Figure 1 (for detailed meaning of layers please refer to report [1]):

1. the Application domain (APP)
2. the Cloud domain (CLD)
3. the Smart Space domain (SSP)
4. the Smart Device domain (SDEV)

Figure 1. The symbloTe high-level architecture

SymbloTe is aiming to create flexible interoperability mechanisms which can be achieved by introducing an incremental deployment of symbloTe functionality across the listed architectural domains (APP, CLD, SSP and SDEV). We assume that this approach will enable platform providers to choose an appropriate level of integration of symbloTe-specific services within their platforms, which will in effect influence the level of platform collaboration and cooperation with other platforms within a symbloTe-enabled ecosystem.

Figure 2 symbloTe Compliance Levels

There are four different Compliance Levels for IoT platforms defined, as depicted in Figure 2. They reflect different interoperability modes, which an IoT platform can support.

Different interoperability modes affect the functionality that needs to be supported by platforms, and require specific symbloTe components to be integrated with existing IoT platforms across different domains.

Current release (Release 3) implementation is aiming to provide components that are supporting Level-1 Compliance (L1). L1 relates to services placed in two domains, APP and CLD, as depicted in Figure 3. IoT platforms which want to become part of the symbloTe ecosystem need to integrate the symbloTe Interworking Interface with their existing components running in the Cloud Domain. This will enable semantic interoperability and open access to IoT services that a platform chooses to register and make discoverable via the symbloTe Core Services. Access to these devices stays under the control of a platform provider, while being enabled through the Interworking Interface. In addition to open access, symbloTe also supports authenticated and authorized access to IoT services.

Figure 3. Level-1 Compliance

3.3 System design for implementation phase

3.3.1 Architectural ideas

The symbloTe Level 1 architecture is defined in D1.4 [14] in the form presented in Figure 4. It is clearly visible, that this set of functional system components repeats the layered idea of the L1 system outline shown in the Figure 4.

Figure 4 Component diagram for Level 1 Compliance

All components represented in Figure 5 are part of Release 3 (except Core Anomaly Detection). In addition, a common library has been introduced, called *symbloTeLibraries*. The main goal of the library is to contain all common model objects and methods used by multiple components, to ease the development and integration process. In addition, since security layer affects all components, *symbloTeLibraries* has been extended to provide security solutions previously designed as a separate component: *Security Handler*.

Detailed descriptions of each component’s features implemented in the current release are described in the following chapters, therefore, in this chapter, we will focus on component design, communication flow and support of the information models.

Figure 5. Release 3 system design – L1 components

3.3.2 Semantic interoperability and data models

The overall objective of symbloTe is to create an interoperability framework for IoT platforms and to enable platform federation. In this scope, achieving semantic interoperability is a key challenge. From the beginning, symbloTe plans to use semantic technologies to bridge the gap between existing and future IoT platforms with a goal to enable interoperability on the semantic level. For detailed description of symbloTe's semantic interoperability level issues, please refer to the Deliverable D2.1 "*Semantics for IoT and Cloud resources*" [3] and Deliverable D2.4 "*Revised Semantics for IoT and Cloud Resources*" [4].

Figure 6 symbloTe Meta Information Model (MIM), current version 0.3

BIM is a special kind of PIM designed to cover the domains of the use cases. It contains, for example, definitions of units and physical properties.

Our current approach is to utilize semantic web technology stack inside the Core Services. Information models are a basis for platform and resources registration, modification and search functionality. To provide better support for this as well as other semantic functionalities, like semantic validation and mappings, an additional component has been created: Semantic Manager. Full description of this component can be found later in the document.

Strict Resource Description Framework (RDF) is currently used internally by Search component. RDF provides description of entities, such as platforms and resources, Registry is providing two options: a simplified API, which uses JSON as a payload as well as an RDF endpoint, allowing to provide semantic description directly. Internally JSON representation is translated into RDF description by Semantic Manager component.

Search is also exposing two ways of querying the data stored in the Core:

- Parameterized query - allows to find resources using basic definitions from CIM model for their filtering
- Full SPARQL query to access all semantic data

The first option provides quite simple interface that allows quickly use search functionality through simple REST endpoint with parameters. The second is more advanced and flexible, but requires creating a proper SPARQL query.

Figure 7 symbloTe Core Information Model (CIM), current version 1.0

3.3.3 Implementation design

One of the first conclusions of the requirements analysis [1] and creation of the first architecture outlines, was that the potential load of requests to the central, core services can be huge. Potentially thousands of end-user client applications are expected to simultaneously access or search for interesting resources in hundreds (from thousands) of sensors/actuators provided by hundreds of IoT platform instances. Although the numbers seem high, this is quite a probable scenario in a fully-fledged, interworking IoT environment.

This leads us to the following implications:

- We are building a large-scale distributed system.
- System architecture has to naturally support horizontal scaling.
- We have to offer a simple REST interface of the Core Services for end-clients, both end-user applications and IoT platforms. It is also possible during implementation, that some of these REST end points will have to be designed in an asynchronous way (e.g. by the call-back mechanisms implementation)
- To be able to handle the load of requests, the internal communication between components should be non-blocking (asynchronous).
- Due to scalability and performance issues, the internal system components, especially in case of the Core Services, have to be designed as autonomous, loosely coupled working services with well-established interfaces.
- We have to minimize single points of failure in the system. This leads us to choose a share-nothing architecture.
- System components have to be responsive (respond in a timely manner, focused on providing rapid and consistent response time), resilient (responsive in the face of failure), elastic (stay responsive under varying workload, no central bottlenecks) and message driven (rely on asynchronous messaging that is also establishing boundaries between components). All these four presumptions are key demands of *Reactive Manifesto* [6]

These implications, that should be met by the implemented system, have motivated our decision to base our design on a *microservice architecture*, which presumes that each component can be characterized by the following properties: isolation, autonomy, single responsibility, exclusive state, asynchronous message passing and mobility [7]. Those properties are in line with the previously-listed key design requirements.

We are basing our implementation on the *Spring* framework (*Spring Boot*, *Spring Cloud* [8]) that facilitates component configuration, services discovery (*Eureka* middle tier load balancer [9]) and tracing (*Zipkin* distributed tracing system [10]). It means we are using already existing and well-established standard, ready-to-use solutions everywhere where it is suitable and do not affect system business logic in a negative way.

As it was pointed out during the analysis phase, we decided to use asynchronous messaging inside the system. This kind of communication is one of the inherent features of the microservice architecture. Without asynchronous messaging microservices cannot reach their full potential.

In our case the internal messaging system of choice is the AMQP [11] standard messaging protocol adopted by OASIS. We are using RabbitMQ [12] server and each separate component is implementing messaging solution using AMQP compliant framework such as RabbitMQ or Spring AMQP [13]. Communication interfaces of each component are described in chapter 4. Examples of payload are available in Appendix. Outside interfaces, designed to be used by client applications and platforms, are RESTful and their definitions and use examples are also referenced in Appendix.

4 Final design of L1 components

This chapter provides detailed information about L1 components that are under the implementation process within Task 2.2. For each component, we are reporting the final list of features to be integrated within Release 3. We are reporting component's general description, information about their interfaces and currently implemented features. YAML definition of REST interfaces and payload examples are included in the Appendix (see Chapter 9). Components are presented in the alphabetical order.

The examples of Release 3 software usage are included in Appendix (par. 9.4). Deliverable “D5.2 – Report on System Integration and Application Development” will contain a detailed description of the platform L1 integration process from the IoT platform owner point of view – this is a practical guide showing how to attempt to achieve Level 1 of Compliance.

4.1 Component: Administration

4.1.1 Administration component description

This component facilitates the control and administration of the symbloTe Core Services by providing a web-based GUI. symbloTe administrators have access to a control panel that allows them to perform management actions and update parameters related to the symbloTe Core Services, such as removing specific platforms from the registry or changing the values of search engine variables to improve ranking. Furthermore, administrators will have access through the web-based interface to internal information, e.g. logs, IoT service popularity data, platform usage/status data or unauthorized user access attempts.

This component will also provide features to non-administrator users. It will enable IoT platforms and applications to register with symbloTe and to receive credentials that are required for the subsequent usage of symbloTe services. We envision guest/trial, regular and premium registrations. It will also be possible to register enablers with symbloTe, with two possible roles:

- 1) as platforms offering domain-specific IoT-related services and
- 2) as applications which use symbloTe to find and access IoT services provided by symbloTe-enabled platforms.

The system should enable IoT platforms to control whether their IoT services appear in search results, subject to the access rights of the query issued to these services i.e., whether the application developer or enabler is registered with the respective IoT platform.

In terms of the Release 3, Administration's main functionalities are:

- providing GUI and server-side logic for symbloTe user registration (e.g. IoT platform owner/administrator);
- Supplies adequate credentials to IoT platforms, enablers and applications by the Core AAM
- providing GUI and server-side logic for IoT platform registration-activation in symbloTe, as well as modification and removal.

The Administration component communicates with the Registry and Core Authorization & Authentication Manager components in a synchronous manner.

4.1.2 Administration component interface

Administration is the only core service layer component that exposes a GUI element. Administration is communicating internally only with the Core components via synchronous RabbitMQ communication. So, besides GUI, there is also a message driven interface for internal communication in Administration. The current set of messages, their meaning, the component that acts as consumer and the payload is shown in Table 1.

Table 1 – Administration interfaces

#	Interface	Name	From	Consumer	Address/Queue	Payload ¹	Response	Description
1	Platform registration (RPC)	platform.creationRequested	AdminUI	Registry	Exchange: symbiote.platform, routing key equal to "Name" column	Platform information	Status (HTTP status code as integer), Platform information	Event requesting creation of new platform
2	Platform modification (RPC)	platform.modificationRequested	AdminUI	Registry	Exchange: symbiote.platform, routing key equal to "Name" column	Platform information	Status (HTTP status code as integer), Platform information	Event requesting modification of existing platform.
3	Platform removal (RPC)	platform.removalRequested	AdminUI	Registry	Exchange: symbiote.platform, routing key equal to "Name" column	Platform information	Status (HTTP status code as integer)	Event requesting removal of existing platform
4	Platform Owner registration (RPC)	symbloTe .AuthenticationAuthorizationManager .platform_register_request	AdminUI	CoreAAM	Exchange: symbloTe .AuthenticationAuthorizationManager , routing key equal to "Name" column	Platform Registration Request	success: Platform Registration Response, failure: ErrorResponse	Platform registration in CAAM, platform_AAM_URL is required to provide list of available login endpoints for symbiote users
5	Application registration (RPC)	symbloTe .AuthenticationAuthorizationManager .application_register_request	AdminUI	CoreAAM	Exchange: symbloTe .AuthenticationAuthorizationManager , routing key equal to "Name" column	User Registration Request	success: User Registration Response, failure: ErrorResponse	Application registration in CAAM, added recovery mail for user friendliness
6	Login (RPC)	symbloTe .AuthenticationAuthorizationManager .login_request	AdminUI	CoreAAM	Exchange: symbloTe .AuthenticationAuthorizationManager , routing key equal to "Name" column	Credentials	token String issued for that Platform Owner	Used when Administration would like to log in on behalf of the user/platform owner.
7	Owned platform instance details (RPC)	symbloTe .AuthenticationAuthorizationManager .ownedPlatformDetails_request	AdminUI	CoreAAM	Exchange: symbloTe .AuthenticationAuthorizationManager , routing key equal to "Name" column	Token	OwnedPlatformDetails	When the Administration wants to retrieve the owned platform instance details for the logged in Platform Owner

¹ Payloads descriptions are available in Appendix, chapter 9.3

4.1.3 Current release features of Administration component

Administration component for current release (R3) has to allow manual registration of (through website interface) a new symbloTe user and new symbloTe platform. This implicates the following features:

- Web pages for:
 - symbloTe administrator / user login
 - form for user registration, providing user certificate after success
 - form for platform owner registration, providing user certificate after success
 - control panel, displaying platform status
 - form for platform registration/activation
 - form for platform details modification
 - form for platform removal/diabling
- Server-side logic for the above-listed web pages/forms implementing component's internal interface described in 4.1.2

4.2 Component: Authentication and Authorization Manager

This component, depending on provisioned configuration can act as:

- Core AAM
- Platform AAM

4.2.1 Authentication and Authorization Manager component description

This component offers mechanisms for the authentication and authorization of symbloTe entities/actors, i.e. users/application developers, IoT platforms, developed applications and clients.

The component provides functionalities for configurable trust relationships between symbloTe and symbloTe-based applications, through the use of X.509 certificates.

AAMs authenticate components belonging to a given IoT platform integrated with symbloTe, that would like to use services offered by the core layer (i.e., resource registration, resource unregistration, resource update, monitoring of the resource availability, search, resource access).

It also authenticates applications (users) registered in the core layer or in an IoT platform integrated with symbloTe, that would like to search and access to resources.

It issues *home* tokens for components and applications that successfully complete the authentication procedure in the relevant AAM. *Home* tokens contain attributes (i.e., roles, properties, permissions) that are used to access to resources and/or services managed by the Core layer / platform / enabler running the AAM which issued that token, according to the Attribute Based Access Control (ABAC) paradigm.

It also revokes *home* tokens when the *expiration date* indicated in the token expires or, asynchronously, when an abnormal, frequent unauthorized use is detected or the user wants to revoke it on purpose.

When the authentication in the core layer is initiated by a component belonging to a given IoT platform federated with symbloTe or by an application registered within a given IoT platform federated with symbloTe, it:

- validates the *home* token previously generated in the aforementioned IoT platform proving it for expiry, signature errors or revoked credentials (token Id, issuer & subject's public keys).
- (optional) for explicitly agreed and defined 'federation' mapping between that platform and the core - converts given home token into a *foreign* token by translating the set of attributes assigned to an entity in a given platform to another set of attributes that characterize the entity in the core layer (this operation is called Attribute Mapping Function)

Manages a public keys revocation collection and a Token Revocation List (TRL), which contain platform and core users' public keys and tokens that were revoked by the users, platform owners or Symbiote Administrator.

4.2.2 Authentication and Authorization Manager component interface

Interfaces REST addresses and AMQP queues are described in relevant interfaces in symbioteSecurity library (par. 5.14, Table 11).

The current list of interfaces is shown in Table 2.

Table 2 – AAM Release 3 interfaces

Operation	From	Type	Request	Response
Get available AAMs	REST client	GET	empty	ResponseEntity<Set<AAM>> with code HTTP:200 on ok and HTTP:500 on error
Get Component certificate	REST client	GET	empty	CA certificate in PEM String format
Manage platform	Administration	AMQP	Platform Management Request	Platform Management Response
get owned platforms instances' details	Administration	AMQP	Platform Owner's Token String	OwnedPlatformDetails
Manage user (application / platform owner)	Administration	AMQP	User Management Request	User Management Response
Get client certificate	REST client	POST	ClientCertificateRequest: - username - password - client identifier - Base64 encoded String with certificate signing request	Success: Base64 encoded String with PEM certificate Error: error status
Get Home Token	Administration	AMQP	Signed LoginRequest	token String issued for that client (user/platform owner client)
Get Home Token	REST client	POST	Signed LoginRequest	Headers with X-Auth-token containing token String for that client
Get Roamed / federated / foreign Token	REST client	POST	Headers with: X-Auth-token containing HOME token String for that client; (opt) X-Auth-Cert containing Base64 encoded PEM Certificate String matching SPK from token	Headers with X-Auth-token containing FOREIGN/ROAMED/FEDERATED token String for that client
Get Guest Token	REST client	GET	empty	Headers with X-Auth-token containing GUEST token String
validation	Symbiote components	AMQP	JWS token String (opt) Base64 encoded PEM Certificate String matching SPK from token	ValidationStatus
validation	REST client	POST	Headers with: X-Auth-token containing HOME token String for that client; (opt) X-Auth-Cert containing Base64 encoded PEM Certificate String matching SPK from token	ValidationStatus
Revoke token	REST client	POST	X-Auth-token containing HOME token String for that client, Username, Password	{"status": <success/failure>}
Revoke certificate	REST client	POST	Username, Password, client_id	{"status": <success/failure>}
Revoke certificate	Administration	AMQP	AAM admin credentials, Base64 encoded PEM Certificate String issued by this AAM	{"status": <success/failure>}
Released attributes provisioning	Administration	AMQP	WIP	{"status": <success/failure>}
Attributes mapping provisioning	Administration	AMQP	WIP	{"status": <success/failure>}

4.2.3 Current release features of Authentication and Authorization Manager

- Authenticates platforms and applications (users) registered in symbloTe core within symbloTe.
- Releases tokens storing trusted attributes, if the authentication process was successful.
- Manages certificates issued for each registered user's clients
- Validates *home* tokens that it has released, by verifying that the token is authentic (by checking the integrity of its signature) and that the expiration date indicated herein has not expired (R3 extension from now on) as well as has not been revoked asynchronously, before the expiration date indicated herein, through the use of a TRL or by communicating directly with the AAM that generated this token. This is called *validation*. For tokens released by other AAMs it also performs certificate chain verification.
- Translates the set of attributes included in a provided *home* token into a new set of attributes in accordance to the explicit federation rules between participating parties (e.g. platforms with the core) and issues the *foreign* token for entities that are not registered within the core layer but are in possession of a valid *home* token that matches the federation contract. This procedure is called *Attributes Mapping Function*.
- Issues *guest* tokens for users that don't have an account in any symbiote AAM and want to try out symbiote services which have public access.

4.3 Component: Cloud-Core Interface

4.3.1 Cloud-Core Interface description

Cloud-Core Interface is working as a gateway created for accessing symbloTe Core Services from the IoT platform's side and symbloTe platform-side components. In other words, it provides endpoints for all elements gathered in the Cloud Domain layer of symbloTe that need access to the symbloTe Core Services (as it is described in Figure 4).

4.3.2 Cloud-Core Interface component interface

For needs of the current release, the outside API of this component is a set of REST endpoints. This is visible from IoT platforms and their supporting symbloTe elements. The internal communication inside the Core Services is event driven and is implemented using RabbitMQ. Description of resources passed to Cloud-Core Interface can be in form of either JSON or RDF document. The current REST interface of Cloud-Core Interface is defined in Appendix in YAML format.

4.3.3 Current release features of Cloud-Core Interface

Current implementation supports both description forms – JSON and RDF document. The currently supported operations include creating, modifying and deleting resources. A new endpoint has been added, allowing platforms to communicate with Core Resource Monitor to pass their current status notifications. Services work in a standard, blocking REST manner, therefore Cloud-Core Interface needs to coordinate synchronous communication

with clients on one side, asynchronous handling of request with the core components on the other side.

4.4 Component: Core Interface

4.4.1 Core Interface description

Core Interface is a core northbound API for accessing symbloTe main core services by third parties. It defines a way of interaction for users and outer clients (i.e. applications and enablers) and plays the role of an I/O gateway to the symbloTe instance of Core Services.

4.4.2 Core Interface component interface

Similarly to Cloud-Core Interface, Core Interface acts as a gateway, allowing access to asynchronously connected core modules on the symbloTe side by opening standard REST endpoints to third parties. The current REST interface of Core Interface is supplied in Appendix in YAML format.

4.4.3 Current release features of Core Interface component

In the current release, Core Interface provides access to the Search module, allowing querying for registered resources using multiple parameters, e.g., resource location or its observed properties, as well as using SPARQL queries.

Apart from querying registered resources, Core Interface provides access to Core Resource Access Monitor, which allows clients to obtain URLs for the resources on the platform side which they would like to access (i.e., a URL of Interworking Interface registered for a specific resource).

It also provides access to Authorization and Authentication Manager by proxying all operations needed to operate with symbloTe components (logging in, checking token revocation, listing available AAM instances, etc.)

4.5 Component: Core Resource Access Monitor

4.5.1 Core Resource Access Monitor description

Core Resource Access Monitor (CRAM) acts as a proxy that redirects applications and enablers to the actual resources offered by symbloTe-enabled platforms. Furthermore, it collects resource access statistics from Resource Access Proxies in order to maintain resource popularity information within the Core Services. Such information is vital as an input to the ranking algorithm used in SymbloTe Core.

4.5.2 Core Resource Access Monitor interfaces

The Core Access Monitor does not expose any REST interfaces. It only communicates with the other Core components by using RabbitMQ. Any need for inter-domain communication, either with applications, or with platform components, is facilitated by the

Core Interface and the Cloud-Core Interface respectively via RabbitMQ too. In Table 3, it is possible to see a summary of CRAM's interfaces.

Table 3 – CRAM interfaces

#	Interface	Name	Msg Type	From	Msg Consumers	Address/Queue	Payload ²	Description
1	Platform Created	symbloTe.platform.created	Event	Registry	CRAM	Exchange: symbiote.platform, routing key equal to "Name" column	Platform information	A new platform was added in the symbloTe system
2	Platform Updated	symbloTe.platform.updated	Event	Registry	CRAM	Exchange: symbiote.platform, routing key equal to "Name" column	Platform information	A platform was updated
3	Platform Deleted	symbloTe.platform.deleted	Event	Registry	CRAM	Exchange: symbiote.platform, routing key equal to "Name" column	Platform Id	A platform was deleted
4	Resource Created	symbloTe.resource.created	Event	Registry	CRAM	Exchange: symbiote.resource, routing key equal to "Name" column	Resource Information	A new resource was added in the symbloTe system
5	Resource Updated	symbloTe.resource.updated	Event	Registry	CRAM	Exchange: symbiote.resource, routing key equal to "Name" column	Resource Information	A resource was updated
6	Resource Deleted	symbloTe.resource.deleted	Event	Registry	CRAM	Exchange: symbiote.resource, routing key equal to "Name" column	Resource Id	A resource was deleted
7	Get Resource Urls	symbloTe.CoreResourceAccessMonitor.coreAPI.get_resource_urls	Event	CRAM	Application (via Core Interface)	Exchange: symbloTe.CoreResourceAccessMonitor, routing key equal to "Name" column	Resource Urls Request	Returns to the application the resource access urls of the requested resource ids
8	Resource Access statistics	symbloTe.CoreResourceAccessMonitor.coreAPI.get_resource_access_stats	Event	RAP (via CloudCoreInterface)	CRAM	Exchange: symbloTe.CoreResourceAccessMonitor, routing key equal to "Name" column	Resource Access Stats	RAP sends resource access stats to CRAM (via CloudCoreInterface)

² Payloads descriptions are available in Appendix, chapter 9.3

4.5.3 Current release features of Core Resource Access Monitor

CRAM for current release has to allow applications/enablers to access resources by getting a list of resource ids and providing their URLs. This implies that CRAM has to offer:

- interfaces to listen for platform/resource events (e.g. creation, modification and deletion)
- an interface to listen for resource URL requests from the applications via the Core Interface and for resource access statistics via Cloud Core Interface
- logic to enable the retrieval of resource URLs from the CRAM's local database providing their ids.
- Calculation of Popularity, which will be used in the SymbloTe ranking algorithm

4.6 Component: Core Resource Monitor

4.6.1 Core Resource Monitor component description

This component must monitor the availability of registered resources to regularly update resource status (online/offline/unavailable) maintained by the Registry. This will ensure that symbloTe search results do not contain resources if their availability cannot be guaranteed, e.g., IoT service types with exclusive access rights (e.g., actuators) are marked unavailable if being used and will thus not appear in search results. It uses scheduled tasks to check resource status. Either resource registrations or application-generated monitoring requests can trigger the scheduling of a monitoring task per resource (or a group of resources).

The component needs to provide appropriate credentials when checking resource status. In addition, it should monitor the load on the registered resources, either in a push or pull style, if IoT platforms and enablers support such functionality. The component may perform functional performance tests on registered resources.

4.6.2 Core Resource Monitor component interface

The Core Resource Monitor does not expose any REST interfaces. It only communicates with the Monitoring component through the Cloud-Core Interface via RabbitMQ. In Table 4, it is possible to see a summary of CRM's interfaces

Table 4 – CRM interfaces

#	Interface	Name	Msg Type	From	Msg Consumers	Address/Queue	Payload ³	Description
1	Monitoring notifications	symbloTe.crm.monitoring.queue	Event	Monitoring	CRM	Exchange: symbloTe.CoreResourceMonitor, routing key: monitoring	Monitoring information	Availability and load information for resources

³ Payloads descriptions are available in Appendix, chapter 9.3

4.6.3 Current release features of Core Resource Monitor

CRM for current release has to wait for notification coming from the Monitoring component, through the Cloud-Core Interface. This implies that CRAM has to offer:

- interfaces to listen for platform/resource monitoring events (e.g. availability, load, etc.)
- a database where to store the information received

4.7 Component: *Interworking Interface*

4.7.1 Interworking Interface description

Interworking Interface acts as a gateway for allowing the communication of symbloTe platform components with the external world (i.e. applications or symbloTe core). Therefore, it simply forwards messages from the external world to the symbloTe components which extend existing platforms and vice versa. It can also act as load balancer when multiple instances of the same platform component are instantiated (e.g. multiple Resource Access Proxy instances). Starting from Release 3, the Interworking Interface component was replaced by nginx.

4.7.2 Interfaces

Interworking Interface exposes REST interfaces in the place of symbloTe platform component, so that they are reachable from the external world. Therefore, it acts like a reverse proxy for the symbloTe platform components. Furthermore, it also acts as a REST proxy for them, since any messages originating from the platform components are forwarded to the external world via the Interworking Interface. Consequently, it does not expose any specific interfaces, but it just processes the request path in order to forward the message to the appropriate recipient.

4.7.3 Current release features of Interworking Interface

As explained above, starting with Release 3 the Interworking Interface was replaced by nginx. So, it does not offer any special features apart from the proxy behavior described earlier. Detailed guidelines for the correct configuration of nginx are presented in the Appendix

4.8 Component: *Monitoring*

4.8.1 Monitoring component description

This component is responsible for two different tasks: monitoring the status of resources and monitoring the access to resources from applications/enablers.

The component will monitor periodically the status of the resources that are being exposed to symbloTe Core Services. It will receive the IDs of the resources that must be monitored.

These ids can belong to IoT resources. The information from the Monitoring will be forwarded to the Resource Monitor residing in the symbloTe Core Services.

4.8.2 Monitoring component interface

The interfaces of this component are described in Table 5.

Table 5 – Monitoring interfaces

#	Interface	Message Type	From	Msg Consumers	Address/Queue/	Payload ⁴	Description
1	Resource registration	RabbitMQ	RH	MONITORING	Exchange: symbloTe.platformExchange Routing key: symbloTe.platformexchange.rh.monitor.register_resources Routing type: routing-direct	Resource information	Event requesting registration of new resource
2	Resource unregistration	RabbitMQ	RH	MONITORING	Exchange: symbloTe.platformExchange Routing key: symbloTe.platformexchange.rh.monitor.unregister_resources Routing type: routing-direct	Resource id	Event requesting unregistration of existing resource
3	Resource update	RabbitMQ	RH	MONITORING	Exchange: symbloTe.platformExchange Routing key: symbloTe.platformexchange.rh.monitor.update_resources Routing key: routing-direct	Resource information	Event requesting update of existing resource

⁴ Payloads descriptions are available in Appendix, chapter 9.3

4.8.3 Current release features of Monitoring

- Monitoring of the availability and load of devices
- Sending this metrics to the core periodically.

4.9 Component: Registration Handler

4.9.1 Registration Handler component description

This component will drive an IoT Platform Provider through the step of registering resources into the symbloTe Core. Registration Handler needs to provide the following information from the symbloTe information model: IoT Device or Composite IoT Service description, Location with its properties, Observed Properties description and name.

Registration Handler sends the metadata describing resources to be registered to the Interworking Interface that will communicate with the Registry. Registry accepts the registration requests, and replies to the Registration Handler (through interworking interface) with a list of IDs generated by symbloTe Core Services for those resources. A similar process is occurring in the case of unregistration of a resource or update of the resource information. Both processes can be triggered by the Registration Handler.

The IoT Platform Provider must be able to define which of its resources are available to use, and under which conditions. A platform does not have to expose all of its resources to symbloTe. Instead, they may opt to reveal just a subset.

4.9.2 Registration Handler component interface

The foreseen interfaces from this component with the Interworking Interface, RAP and monitoring are shown in Table 6.

Table 6 – Registration Handler interfaces

#	Interface	Message Type	From	Msg Consumers	Address/Queue/Exchange type	Payload ⁵	Description
1	Resource registration	RabbitMQ	RH	INTERWOKING INTERFACE	Exchange: symbloTe.InterworkingInterface routing key: symbloTe.InterworkingInterface.registrationHandler.register_resources Routing type: RPC	Resource information	Event requesting registration of new resource
2	Resource unregistration	RabbitMQ	RH	INTERWOKING INTERFACE	Exchange: symbloTe.InterworkingInterface routing key:symbloTe.InterworkingInterface.registrationHandler.unregister_resources Routing type: RPC	Resource id	Event requesting unregistration of existing resource
3	Resource update	RabbitMQ	RH	INTERWOKING INTERFACE	Exchange: symbloTe.InterworkingInterface routing key: symbloTe.InterworkingInterface.registrationHandler.update_resources Routing type: RPC	Resource information	Event requesting update of existing resource
4	Resource registration	RabbitMQ	RH	RAP	Exchange: symbloTe.platformExchange Routing key: symbloTe.platformexchange.rh.rap.register_resources Routing type: routing-direct	Resource information	Event requesting registration of new resource
5	Resource unregistration	RabbitMQ	RH	RAP	Exchange: symbloTe.platformExchange Routing key: symbloTe.platformexchange.rh.rap.unregister_resources Routing type: routing-direct	Resource id	Event requesting unregistration of existing resource
6	Resource update	RabbitMQ	RH	RAP	Exchange: symbloTe.platformExchange Routing key: symbloTe.platformexchange.rh.rap.update_resources Routing type: routing-direct	Resource information	Event requesting update of existing resource
7	Resource registration	RabbitMQ	RH	MONITORING	Exchange: symbloTe.platformExchange Routing key: symbloTe.platformexchange.rh.monitor.register_resources Routing type: routing-direct	Resource information	Event requesting registration of new resource
8	Resource unregistration	RabbitMQ	RH	MONITORING	Exchange: symbloTe.platformExchange Routing key:	Resource id	Event requesting unregistration of existing

⁵ Payloads descriptions are available in Appendix, chapter 9.3

					symbloTe.platformexchange.rh.monitor.unregister_resources Routing type: routing-direct		resource
9	Resource update	RabbitMQ	RH	MONITORING	Exchange: symbloTe.platformExchange Routing key: symbloTe.platformexchange.rh.monitor.update_resources Routing key: routing-direct	Resource information	Event requesting update of existing resource
10	Resources Information	REST	Platform Owner	RH	GET /resources	None	Get the list of resources which have been registered to the Core
11	Resources Information	REST	Platform Owner	RH	GET /resource/{internalResourceId}	None	Get information of a particular resource given its platform's internal ID
12	Resource registration	REST	Platform Owner	RH	POST /resource	Resource information	Registers a resource in the core
13	Resource registration	REST	Platform Owner	RH	POST /resources	List of resources information	Register a list of resources in the core
14	Resource update	REST	Platform Owner	RH	PUT /resource	Resource information	Updates the information about a resource in the core
15	Resource update	REST	Platform Owner	RH	PUT /resources	List of resources information	Updates the information of several resources in the core
16	Resource unregistration	REST	Platform Owner	RH	DELETE /resource/{internalResourceId}	None	Unregister a resource on the core
17	Resource unregistration	REST	Platform Owner	RH	DELETE /resources	None	Unregister a list of resources on the core

4.9.3 Current release features of Registration Handler component

As a proxy to the core for resource registration management, the current implementation supports:

- Resource registration/update/unregistration through local files on startup
- Resource registration/update/unregistration through remote files on startup
- Resource registration/update/unregistration through a REST interface
- Plug-in architecture to allow for the development of new sources of resources information
- Notification or events on resource registration status to any other component on the platform via message queue

4.10 Component: Registry

4.10.1 Registry component description

This component handles registration of symbloTe objects, i.e. platforms and resources. After registering, IoT platforms can add their resources that they want to make discoverable via symbloTe.

Registry receives data from other modules via RabbitMQ asynchronous messaging protocol and after verification, saves it in Mongo database. Service strongly relies on communication with Semantic Manager and stores also data provided by that module. That way, fulfillment of information from/to RDF for each resource is provided and that responsibility is moved to other component.

The component handles verification of the data provided by interfaces, including uniqueness of identifiers given by other modules. Uniqueness is enforced both within and across IoT platform boundaries, which is critical, e.g., in the case of roaming IoT devices.

Registry module is a part of symbloTe Core Services. It communicates with other modules using asynchronous, event driven scheme.

4.10.2 Registry component interface

As Registry is strictly a core module, the only communication it supports is via RabbitMQ asynchronous messaging. Its interface, based on asynchronous exchanges and routing keys, is described in Table 7.

Table 7 – Registry interfaces

#	Interface	Name	Message Type	From	Msg Consumers	Address/Queue	Payload ⁶	Description
1	Platform Registration (RPC)	platform.creationRequested	event	Administration	Registry	Exchange: symbiote.platform, routing key equal to "Name" column	Platform information, including platform unique id	Event requesting creation of new platform
1a	RPC response	platform.creationPerformed	event	Registry	Administration	Temporary queue used only for RPC response	Status (HTTP status code as integer) Platform information	Response to the RPC platform creation request
1b	Message (fanout)	platform.created	event	Registry	Search cRAM	Exchange: symbiote.platform, routing key equal to "Name" column	Platform information, including platform unique id	Event informing that new platform has been successfully created in database.
2	Platform modification (RPC)	platform.modificationRequested	event	Administration	Registry	Exchange: symbiote.platform, routing key equal to "Name" column	Platform information, including platform unique ID	Event requesting modification of existing platform.
2a	RPC response	platform.modificationPerformed	event	Registry	Administration	Temporary queue used only for RPC response	Status (HTTP status code as integer) Platform information	Response to the RPC platform modification request
2b	Message (fanout)	platform.modified	event	Registry	Search cRAM	Exchange: symbiote.platform, routing key equal to "Name" column	Platform information, including platform unique id	Event informing that platform description has been successfully changed.
3	Platform removal (RPC)	platform.removalRequested	event	Administration	Registry	Exchange: symbiote.platform, routing key equal to "Name" column	Platform information, including platform unique ID	Event requesting removal of existing platform
3a	RPC response	platform.removalPerformed	event	Registry	Administration	Temporary queue used only for RPC response	Status (HTTP status code as integer) Platform information	Response to the RPC platform removal request
3b	Message (fanout)	platform.removed	event	Registry	Search cRAM	Exchange: symbiote.platform, routing key equal to "Name" column	Platform information, including platform unique id	Event informing that platform with specified id has been deleted from the repository

⁶ Payloads descriptions are available in Appendix, chapter 9.3

4	Resource Registration (RPC)	resource.creationRequested	event	Cloud-Core Interface	Registry	Exchange: symbiote.resource, routing key equal to "Name" column	Resources information including unique ids (list in JSON or RDF description), description type, corresponding Platform ID and token	Event requesting creation of new resource
4a	RPC response	resource.creationPerformed	event	Registry	Cloud-Core Interface	Temporary queue used only for RPC response	Status (HTTP status code as integer), message, description type and Resources information (list as JSON) including RDF description	Response to the RPC resource creation request
4b	Message (fanout)	resource.created	event	Registry	Search cRAM	Exchange: symbiote.resource, routing key equal to "Name" column	List containing Resources information, including resource unique id	Event informing that new resource has been successfully created in database.
5	Resource modification (RPC)	resource.modificationRequested	event	Cloud-Core Interface	Registry	Exchange: symbiote.resource, routing key equal to "Name" column	Resources information including unique ids (list in JSON or RDF description), description type, corresponding Platform ID and token	Event requesting modification of existing resource.
5a	RPC response	resource.modificationPerformed	event	Registry	Cloud-Core Interface	Temporary queue used only for RPC response	Status (HTTP status code as integer), message, description type and Resources information (list as JSON) including RDF description	Response to the RPC resource modification request
5b	Message (fanout)	resource.modified	event	Registry	Search cRAM	Exchange: symbiote.resource, routing key equal to "Name" column	Resource information, including resource unique id	Event informing that resource description has been successfully changed.
6	Resource removal (RPC)	resource.removalRequested	event	Cloud-Core Interface	Registry	Exchange: symbiote.resource, routing key equal to "Name" column	Resources information including unique ids (list in JSON or RDF description), description type, corresponding Platform ID and token	Event requesting removal of existing resource
6a	RPC response	resource.removalPerformed	event	Registry	Cloud-Core Interface	Temporary queue used only for RPC response	Status (HTTP status code as integer), message, description type and Resources information (list as JSON) including RDF description	Response to the RPC resource removal request
6b	Message (fanout)	resource.removed	event	Registry	Search cRAM	Exchange: symbiote.resource, routing key equal to "Name" column	Resource information, including resource unique id	Event informing that resource with specified id has been deleted from the repository
7	Get Resources for Platform (RPC)	platform.resourcesRequested	event	Administration	Registry	Exchange: symbiote.platform, routing key equal to "Name" column	Platform ID and token	Event requesting a list of Resources belonging to given Platform

7a	RPC Response	platform.resourcesReplied	event	Registry	Administration	Temporary queue used only for RPC response	List of resources in JSON String	Response to request for a list of Resources of a given Platform
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4.10.3 Current release features of Registry component

For the current release, Registry component manages to fulfill its basic tasks, which is registering, modifying and removing platforms and resources. It uses no-SQL Mongo DB for its storage. The communication protocol is also established, so that other modules can be notified of performed tasks.

Registry uses basic JSON format to describe both platforms and resources.

4.11 Component: Resource Access Proxy

4.11.1 Resource Access Proxy component description

This component enables symbloTe-compliant access to resources within an IoT platform (or enabler acting as a platform).

It must receive incoming access requests from applications/enablers using a symbloTe-compliant communication protocol and data format. A request must contain a unique identifier assigned to a resource. It must check that a token included in the request is valid and that access to a particular resource can be granted.

The data generated by IoT platform must be returned in a format which complies with the symbloTe information model. Otherwise, optionally, a Platform Information Model can be loaded into the RAP, providing the related owl file, in order to extend the CIM with custom properties.

4.11.2 Resource Access Proxy component interface

The Resource Access Proxy exposes both REST / OData and RabbitMQ interfaces. It communicates with the Registration Handler component via RabbitMQ, and exposing REST / OData-like interfaces [16] for direct resources' access. An additional interface is used for push mechanism, where notifications are linked via WebSocket with the client application.

In Table 8, it is possible to see a summary of RAP's interfaces.

Table 8 – RAP interfaces

#	Interface	Name	Message Type	From	Msg Consumers	Address/Queue	Payload ⁷	Description
1	Resource registration	symbloTe.rap.registrationHandler.register_resources	RabbitMQ	RH	RAP	Exchange: symbloTe.rap Routing key: routing-direct	Resource information	Event requesting registration of new resource
2	Resource registration	symbloTe.rap.registrationHandler.unregister_resources	RabbitMQ	RH	RAP	Exchange: symbloTe.rap Routing key: routing-direct	Resource id	Event requesting unregistration of existing resource
3	Resource registration	symbloTe.rap.registrationHandler.update_resources	RabbitMQ	RH	RAP	Exchange: symbloTe.rap Routing key: routing-direct	Resource information	Event requesting update of existing resource
4a	Resource access read	/rap/Sensor/{resourceId}	REST	Interworking Interface	RAP	GET	None - replies with the value of the resource	Event reading the value of a resource
4b	Resource access read	/rap/Sensors({resourceId})/Observations?\$top=1	OData	Interworking Interface	RAP	GET	None - replies with the value of the resource	Event reading the value of a resource
5a	Resource access read history	/rap/Sensor/{resourceId}/history	REST	Interworking Interface	RAP	GET	None - replies with the history values of the resource	Event reading the value of a resource
5b	Resource access read history	/rap/Sensors({resourceId})/Observations	OData	Interworking Interface	RAP	GET	None - replies with the history values of the resource	Event reading the value of a resource
6a	Resource access write	/rap/Service/{resourceId}	REST	Interworking Interface	RAP	POST	{ "inputParameters": [{ "name": "param_name", "value": "param_value" }, ..] }	Event writing the value of a resource
6b	Resource	/rap/ActuatingService{resourceId}	OData	Interworking	RAP	PUT	{	Event writing the

⁷ Payloads descriptions are available in Appendix, chapter 9.3

	access write			Interface			<pre> <inputparameters": "name":="" "param_name",="" "param_value"="" "value":="" ..="" <="" [=""]="" pre="" {="" },=""> </inputparameters":></pre>	value of a resource
7	Resource notifications	/notification	WebSocket	Interworking Interface	RAP	client / server	the value of the resource	Event reading the value of a resource

4.11.3 Current release features of Resource Access Proxy component

RAP for current release has to allow applications/enablers to access resource data both for reading and writing values. This implies that RAP has to offer:

- interfaces to register / unregister / update resources from the platform, receiving requests from the Registration Handler
- interfaces to access to resources for reading events (current value and history readings)
- interfaces to access to resources for writing events (with input parameters included in the body of the request)
- logic to support push mechanism via WebSocket
- logic to support extended Platform Information Models (and BIMs).

4.12 Component: Search

4.12.1 Search component description

This component allows developers of applications and enablers to search for information stored in symbloTe Core, such as description of the resources and platforms. To perform search operation two types of requests are possible:

- a parameterized query that allows to find resources fulfilling basic filtering criteria (corresponding to the information that is stored in CIM and BIM). Internally this request is translated into appropriate SPARQL request to perform the search.
- a SPARQL query, which is a dedicated RDF query language

To provide its functionality Search component stores the representations of the symbloTe objects registered in the Core (such as platforms and their resources) in Apache Jena RDF triplestore. Any necessary translations into RDF and ontology operations (such as mappings) are done by separate component, Semantic Manager (which is described elsewhere in the deliverable).

4.12.2 Search component interface

Search communicates with other modules using asynchronous messaging based on RabbitMQ AMQP implementation. Its interface, based on asynchronous exchanges and routing keys, is described in the following table.

4.12.3 Current release features of Search component

Current release (R3) of the Search is based on Apache Jena, version 3.1.0. Component is integrated with latest symbloTe information models: CIM v1.0, MIM v0.3, BIM 0.3. Those models, as well as all platform-specific information models registered to the Core and RDF descriptions of platforms and resources, are stored in the Jena triplestore.

Search is also providing query mechanisms: translation of the parameterized query into SPARQL and ability to perform the search and return information about found resources

as a SearchResponse (see Appendix 9.3). It also allows to directly use SPARQL query and specify output format.

Search is integrated with event messaging:

- Registry component creates an event that announces new platforms and resources being added, which triggers storage of their RDF descriptions in Search. Handling of the removal and update of those resources is also performed using SPARQL Update extension to the SPARQL language.
- Core Interface component triggers search. In case of simple search parameters are used to create appropriate SPARQL query which is used to search for the resources fitting the criteria. Information about found resources is collected and send back to the client. In case of SPARQL query request is modified to include information required for filtering of the results according to the access policies.

Search communicates with other modules using asynchronous messaging based on RabbitMQ AMQP implementation. Its interface, based on asynchronous exchanges and routing keys, is described in Table 9.

Table 9 – Search interfaces

#	Interface	Name	Message Type	From	Msg Consumers	Address/Queue	Payload ⁸	Description
1	Resource query (RPC)	resource.searchRequested	event	Core Interface	Search	Exchange: symbiote.resource, routing key equal to "Name" column	Query parameters	Event requesting query results for supplied query parameters
2	RPC response	resource.searchPerformed	event	Search	Core Interface	Temporary queue used only for RPC response	Search Response	Query results, containing resources matching specified parameters
3	SPARQL query (RPC)	resource.sparqlSearchRequested	event	Core Interface, Semantic Manager	Search	Exchange: symbiote.resource, routing key equal to "Name" column	SPARQL query, format of the response output	Event requesting executing sparql query with specified output format.
4	SPARQL RPC response	resource.sparqlSearchPerformed	event	Search	Core Interface, Semantic Manager	Temporary queue used only for RPC response	SPARQL Search Response	SPARQL results in the specified format

⁸ Payloads descriptions are available in Appendix, chapter 9.3

4.13 Component: Semantic Manager

4.13.1 Semantic Manager component description

Semantic Manager was created as a specialized component to handle RDF translation and validation processes of the Core functionalities. It uses Apache Jena to store information models: CIM v1.0, MIM v0.3 and BIM v0.3. It also stores additional platform specific PIMs to be used for validating their resources.

Component is providing its functionalities to other components, mainly Registry and Administration.

4.13.2 Semantic Manager component interface

Semantic Manager communicates with other modules using asynchronous messaging based on RabbitMQ AMQP implementation. Its interface, based on asynchronous exchanges and routing keys, is described in Table 10.

Table 10 – Semantic Manager interfaces

#	Interface	Name	Message Type	From	Msg Consumers	Address/Queue	Payload ⁹	Description
1	Platform model validation	platform.model.validationRequested	event	Administration	Semantic Manager	Exchange: symbiote.platform, routing key equal to "Name" column	RDFInfo	Event requesting validation of the platform model (PIM)
2	RPC response	platform.model.validationPerformed	event	Semantic manager	Registry	Temporary queue used only for RPC response	PIMMetaModelValidationResult	Response to the validation request, contains validation status as well as basic information about the validated object
3	Platform instance validation	platform.instance.validationRequested	event	Registry	Semantic Manager	Exchange: symbiote.platform, routing key equal to "Name" column	RDFInfo	Event requesting validation of the platform description according to the model (MIM/PIM)
4	RPC response	platform.model.validationPerformed	event	Semantic manager	Registry	Temporary queue used only for RPC response	PIMInstanceValidationResult	Response to the validation request, contains validation status as well as basic information about the validated platform
5	Resource instance validation	resource.instance.validationRequested	event	Registry	Semantic Manager	Exchange: symbiote.resource, routing key equal to "Name" column	CoreResourceRegistryRequest	Event requesting validation of the resource description according to the model (BIM/PIM)
6	RPC response	resource.instance.validationPerformed	event	Semantic manager	Registry	Temporary queue used only for RPC response	ResourceInstanceValidationResult	Response to the validation request, contains validation status as well as basic information about the validated resource

⁹ Payloads descriptions are available in Appendix, chapter 9.3

7	Translate BIM resource to RDF	platform.instance.translationRequested	event	Registry	Semantic Manager	Exchange: symbiote.platform, routing key equal to "Name" column	CoreResourceRegistryRequest	Event requesting translation of BIM resource description into RDF
8	RPC response	resource.instance.translationPerformed	event	Semantic manager	Registry	Temporary queue used only for RPC response	ResourceInstanceValidationResult	Response to the translation request, contains validation status as well as basic information about the resource (including the RDF)

4.13.3 Current release features of Semantic Manager component

The following features of the Semantic Manager are released:

1. Storing of PIM – All platform specific information models that are registered in the Core are saved in the Jena triplestore of Semantic Manager.
2. Validation
 - a. Semantic Manager performs a validation of PIM – meta models and platform RDF descriptions.
 - b. Semantic Manager performs a validation of resource RDF description which checks if the description is correct wrt of the declared meta model (PIM or BIM).
3. Translation
 - a. Semantic Manager performs a translation of platform objects (used in communication between Administration and Registry components for example) into RDF, so it can be stored and accessed in the Search component.
 - b. Semantic Manager performs a translation of resource objects (used by BIM-related platforms to describe resources for registration/update/delete) into RDF, so it can be stored and accessed in the Search component.

4.14 Library: *symbloTeLibraries*

4.14.1 *symbloTeLibraries* component description

To provide a support for developers and ease integration step a dedicated library has been created called *symbloTeLibraries*. Its main feature is to define all payloads used in both REST API as well as messaging communication. Also, some of the model classes, especially those that represent entities defined in CIM and MIM, such as *Resource*, *StationarySensor*, *Actuator*, *WGS84Location* etc., are included in *symbloTeLibraries*.

All of the payloads as well as model classes have been divided into two packages: *cloud* and *core*, depending on the origin of the component that defines particular set of classes. In addition, Enabler related common classes have been added to *enabler* package.

Some of the utility classes, containing common, symbloTe related operations are also expected to be added to *symbloTeLibraries*. One of such expansion happened during inclusion of security layer into development. It required all components to integrate with common security operations such as e.g. validation of the tokens, checking of revocation and challenger/response operation. For that a new package *security* has been added, and utility classes have been introduced to help in communication between components and respective (cloud or core) *Authentication and Authorization Manager* to perform security operations.

4.14.2 Current release features of *symbloTeLibraries*

4.14.2.1 *Models, payloads, methods*

List of features of the component with regard of models, payloads and methods included:

- Model classes representing CIM- and MIM-defined entities
- Payloads of Cloud-Core Interface endpoints
- Payloads of Core Interface endpoints
- Payloads of internal messaging in the Core

4.14.2.2 *Security layer features in symbloTeLibraries*

The security features provided for SymbloTe components are in the *eu.h2020.symbiote.security* package of the shared library. This security features, known as Security Handler in the component diagrams, provide a layer with utilities for local security operations as well as communication with symbiote AAM instances, be it on different platforms or in the core. Last but not least it also offers a wallet allowing clients to manage their certificates, tokens and other security artifacts such as:

- Tokens request, validation and management
- Certificates request and management
- Signing of payloads to guarantee peer authenticity on requests using a challenge-response procedure

These features are provided by getting an instance of the *eu.h2020.symbiote.security.SecurityHandler* class which has the following interface:

Table 11 – Security Handler interfaces

Method name	Input	Output	Description
getAvailableAAMs	None	List<AAM>	Get a list of all currently available security endpoints to symbiote
requestCoreToken	String username String password	Token	Request core token using one's Symbiote Core Account.
requestForeignTokens	List<AAM> aams	Map<String, Token>	Requests federated Platform tokens using acquired Core token. Given a list of AAM instances and a Core Token saved in the session, it will use it to get a valid token from each instance on the input list.
logout	None	None	Clears the token wallet (home and core)
getHomeToken	None	Token	Get the home token from the local token wallet
getCoreToken	None	Token	Get the core token from the local token wallet
certificateValidation	KeyStore p12Certificate	Boolean	Validates the certificate used by the user in challenge-response operations against the exposed Core AAM root CA certificate. It receives the local certificate store issued either by the Platform or the Core AAM and returns its validity

verifyCoreToken	Token coreToken	ValidationStatus	Verify the validity of a core token. It will return the token status if it's either valid, valid offline, expired, revoked or invalid
verifyPlatformToken	AAM aam	ValidationStatus	Validates the given token against the exposed relevant AAM certificate. It will return the token status if it's either valid, valid offline, expired, revoked or invalid
	Token platformToken		

Since Security Handler is a part of the security features implemented in WP3, some additional functionality will be part of further developments:

- Certificates acquisition,
- Token acquisition - login 2.0,
- Challenge-response methods,
- ABAC policies resolution helper methods.

5 Components / services basic information tables

This chapter contains all basic information about symbloTe system components implemented for the Release 2. For better reading purpose, the information is presented in tabular style for each component in alphabetical order. The only exception holds for the Interworking Interface Component (this has been replaced by NGINX).

5.1 Administration

Component/service name	Administration
URL of source codes	https://github.com/symbiote-h2020/Administration
URL of Javadoc documentation	https://symbiote-h2020.github.io/Administration/doxygen/
List of features included	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • security -enabled user registration • securtiy-enabled platform owner registration • provisioning of certificates after registration • platform registration/modification/removal

5.2 Authentication and Authorization Manager

Component/service name	Authentication and Authorization Manager
URL of source codes	https://github.com/symbiote-h2020/AuthenticationAuthorizationManager
URL of Javadoc documentation	https://symbiote-h2020.github.io/AuthenticationAuthorizationManager/doxygen/
List of features included	<p>Registration of a new application (actor/user) in the core AAM through Administration UI and in the platform AAM by means of the platform owner</p> <p>Obtaining foreign token using home token</p> <p>Retrieval of the AAM certificates</p> <p>Tokens & certificates validation against:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - signatures and expirations, - cross-aam comms for foreign tokens validation, - (WIP) forged trust chain (offline validation), - (WIP) revoked credentials. <p>(WIP) Fine grained Issuing actors clients' certificates (using CSRs, user, password)</p> <p>(WIP) Login with signed username and clientId tuple (issuing home tokens)</p> <p>Login with home tokens (issuing foreign tokens)</p> <p>(WIP) Login for guest actors (issuing guest tokens)</p> <p>(WIP) Revoking credentials</p>

5.3 Cloud-Core Interface

Component/service name	Cloud-Core Interface
URL of source codes	https://github.com/symbiote-h2020/CloudCoreInterface
URL of Javadoc documentation	https://symbiote-h2020.github.io/CloudCoreInterface/doxygen/
List of features included	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • REST endpoints for Registration Handler requests implemented • asynchronous messaging (AMQP) interface implemented (to publish messages to other components)

5.4 Core Interface

Component/service name	Core Interface
URL of source codes	https://github.com/symbiote-h2020/CoreInterface
URL of Javadoc documentation	https://symbiote-h2020.github.io/CoreInterface/doxygen/
List of features included	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • synchronous REST endpoint for receiving parametrized queries from end-user applications and responding with list of resources implemented • asynchronous messaging (AMQP) interface implemented (to proxy queries to Search component and receiving results)

5.5 Core Resource Access Monitor

Component/service name	Core Resource Access Monitor
URL of source codes	https://github.com/symbiote-h2020/CoreResourceAccessMonitor
URL of Javadoc documentation	https://symbiote-h2020.github.io/CoreResourceAccessMonitor/doxygen/
List of features included	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • asynchronous messaging (AMQP) interfaces for listening to platform/resource events • redirection to actual resources by providing the resource urls to the applications (via the CoreInterface), after verification and validation of the provided tokens. • collecting resource access statistics from Resource Access Proxy • Calculating popularity of resources

5.6 Core Resource Monitor

Component/service name	Core Resource Monitor
URL of source codes	https://github.com/symbiote-h2020/CoreResourceMonitor
URL of Javadoc documentation	https://symbiote-h2020.github.io/CoreResourceMonitor/doxygen/
List of features included	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Providing local storage for resource status (e.g. availability, load, etc.) in internal database

5.7 Interworking Interface

Replaced by nginx. Configuration details are presented in the Appendix.

5.8 Monitoring

Component/service name	Monitoring
URL of source codes	https://github.com/symbiote-h2020/Monitoring
URL of Javadoc documentation	Not published yet
List of features included	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Icinga2 server has been installed in a public machine in order to enable test by partners without the need of installing Icinga2.

5.9 Registration Handler

Component/service name	Registration Handler
URL of source codes	https://github.com/symbiote-h2020/RegistrationHandler
URL of Javadoc documentation	https://symbiote-h2020.github.io/RegistrationHandler/doxygen/
List of features included	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Rest interfaces has been implemented Storage in <i>mongo db</i> is being done messaging (AMQP) has been implemented. They you communicate using the RPC RabbitMQ communication pattern with Interworking Interface and Routing-direct RabbitMQ communication pattern with RAP component.

5.10 Registry

Component/service name	Registry
URL of source codes	https://github.com/symbiote-h2020/Registry
URL of Javadoc documentation	https://symbiote-h2020.github.io/Registry/doxygen/
List of features included	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> asynchronous messaging (AMQP) interface implemented (to receive event messages from Administration component and publish messages to other components) Platform, Resource and Location persistence layer implemented providing a unique ID for every registered object supported creation, modification and removal of Platform/Resource (delivered via AMQP message) supported

5.11 Resource Access Proxy

Component/service name	Resource Access Proxy
URL of source codes	https://github.com/symbiote-h2020/ResourceAccessProxy

URL of Javadoc documentation	https://symbiote-h2020.github.io/RegistrationHandler/doxygen/
List of features included	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • asynchronous messaging (AMQP) interface implemented (to receive registration messages from Resource Handler) • Internal storage of Platform and Resource IDs mapping • translating Platform and Resource IDs to forward requests to IoT platforms • REST support to access to resources • OData support to access to resources • Filtering support for resources historical data • Internal asynchronous messaging (AMQP) interface implemented (to decouple generic rap features from platforms' proprietary access to resources) • WebSocket implementation for push mechanism • Custom information model support (BIM, PIM) with OData

5.12 Search

Component/service name	Search
URL of source codes	https://github.com/symbiote-h2020/Search
URL of Javadoc documentation	https://symbiote-h2020.github.io/Search/doxygen/
List of features included	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • asynchronous messaging (AMQP) interface implemented (to receive event messages from Registry and queries from Core Interface) • saving Platforms and Resources in triplets store (JENA) implemented (RDFs in compliance with CIM and MIM supported) • AMQP endpoint for receiving and translating parameterized queries into SPARQL • AMQP endpoint for SPARQL queries • querying the JENA database with SPARQL query and creating JSON response containing resource information implemented

5.13 Semantic Manager

Component/service name	Semantic Manager
URL of source codes	https://github.com/symbiote-h2020/SemanticManager
URL of Javadoc documentation	https://github.com/symbiote-h2020/SemanticManager/doxygen
List of features included	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stores information models: CIM, MIM, BIM • Stores platform specific information models (PIMs) • Provides validation of information models and entity RDF descriptions • Provides translation of BIM-compliant resource objects into

	RDF
--	-----

5.14 symbloTeLibraries

Component/service name	symbloTeLibraries
URL of source codes	https://github.com/symbiote-h2020/SymbloTeLibraries
URL of Javadoc documentation	https://github.com/symbiote-h2020/SymbloTeLibraries/doxygen
List of features included	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Contains payload definitions for REST and messaging communication• Contains model classes used in more than one component• Exposes security-related functionality for other components

6 Conclusions

The current document is the report of the final implementation of symbloTe software related to L1 compliancy. The main outcome of this work at the current stage is the source code and its documentation, published as an open source project in the GitHub service: <https://github.com/symbiote-h2020>.

There are 14 main software components implemented included in Release 3, 4 stub projects and several 6 supporting projects with separate repositories – all gathered in two GitHub super-projects: SymbioteCore and SymbioteCloud.

The main implemented modules are: Administration, Authentication and Authorization Manager, Cloud-Core Interface, Core Interface, Core Resource Access Monitor, Core Resource Monitor, Interworking Interface, Monitoring, Registration Handler, Registry, Resource Access Proxy, Search, Semantic Manager and Security Handler (contained into the symbioteLibraries).

The supporting projects are: CoreConfigService, CloudConfigService and two versions (core and cloud) of EurekaService and ZipkinService.

The symbloTe software final release (Release 3) is planned for the end of August 2017.

7 Definitions, acronyms, abbreviations

AAM	Authentication and Authorization Manager
AMQP	Advanced Message Queuing Protocol
API	Application Programming Interface
APP	Application Domain
BIM	Best Practice Information Model
CIM	Core Information Model
CLD	Cloud Domain
CRAM	Core Resource Access Monitor, one of symbloTe core software components
ID	Identifier
IM	Information Model
IoT	Internet of Things
JENA	Free and open source Java framework for building Semantic Web and Linked Data applications
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
JSON-LD	JSON-based Serialization for Linked Data
L1	Level 1 of Compliance – symbloTe compliance level related to Application and Cloud domains
MIM	Meta Information Model
PIM	Platform-Specific Information Model
QoS	Quality of Service
RDF	Resource Description Framework
RDFa	Resource Description Framework in Attributes
RDFS	RDF Schema
REST	Representational State Transfer
SDEV	Smart Device Domain
SPARQL	SPARQL Protocol and RDF Query Language
SSP	Smart Space Domain
symbloTe	Symbiosis of Smart Objects across IoT Environments
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier
URL	Uniform Resource Locator
YAML	YAML Ain't Markup Language

8 References

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9 Appendix – Interfaces definitions, communication messages payloads and examples

9.1 Cloud-Core Interface – Swagger (YAML) representation of API and payload

YAML definition of Cloud-Core Interface API and payloads will be included in deliverable “D5.2 – Report on System Integration and Application Development”. However, it is mentioned here because it was a part of D2.2 Appendix [5].

9.2 Core Interface – Swagger (YAML) representation of API and payload

YAML definition of Core Interface API and payloads will be included in deliverable “D5.2 – Report on System Integration and Application Development”. However, it is mentioned here because it was a part of D2.2 Appendix [5].

9.3 Payload definitions

9.3.1 Core side payload definitions

9.3.1.1 Platform

Describes the platform in Core communication. Contains the symbloTe-generated unique id of the platform (*platformId*), as well as information about the platform, which is provided using the Admin component.

```
Platform {
    platformId:           String
    name:                 String
    description:          String
    url:                  String
    informationModelId:   String
}
```

9.3.1.2 Resource

Describes the resource in Core communication. Contains the unique symbloTe-generated id of the resource (*id*), information about the resource (*name*, *owner* and *description*), list of properties observed by this resource (*observedProperties*), base access URL of the resource (*resourceURL* – should point to the *Interworking Interface* that handles this particular resource), resource’s location (*location*), feature of interest for the resource (*featureOfInterest*) and the id of the platform this resource belongs to (*platformId*).

```
Resource {
    id:                   String
```

```
    name:                String
    owner:               String
    description:         String
    observedProperties:  List<String>
    resourceURL:         String
    location:            Location
    featureOfInterest   String
    platformId:         String
}
```

9.3.1.3 Location

Object representing location of the resource. Contains unique symbloTe-generated id of the Location (*id*), name and description of the location and geo-parameters of the location.

```
Location {
    id:                String
    name:              String
    description:       String
    latitude:          Double
    longitude:         Double
    altitude:          Double
}
```

9.3.1.4 Search parameters

Following payload contains a list of optional parameters that can be used in the *HTTP GET* query string to search for resources advertised in symbloTe using *REST* endpoint of the *CoreInterface*. Possible search parameters include: platform info (it's id, name and owner), resource info (it's id, name and description), location resource is located in (using location name and/or distance from particular location) as well as list of observed properties by the resource.

```
Query parameters {
    platform_id:       String
    platform_name:     String
    owner:             String
    name:              String
    id:                String
    description:       String
    location_name:     String
}
```

```
location_lat: Double
location_long: Double
max_distance: Integer
observed_property: List<String>
resource_type: String
}
```

9.3.1.5 Search response

This payload represents single answer to the search query (search query returns list of *QueryResourceResults*). Response correlates strictly to internal Core *Resource* payload from point 9.3.1.2, with main differences being: access URL of the resource is omitted from this response (granting access link to the resource is done using *resourceUrls* endpoint of Cloud Interface) and resource location is represented in the flat JSON representation (instead of nested *Location* object). Also not only id of the platform that found resource belongs to is returned, but also its name.

```
QueryResourceResult {
    id: String
    name: String
    description: String
    owner: String
    platformId: String
    platformName: String
    locationName: String
    locationLatitude: Double
    locationLongitude: Double
    locationAltitude: Double
    observedProperty: List<String>
    resourceType: List<String>
}
```

9.3.1.6 Resource Urls Request

```
ResourceUrlsRequest {
    idList: List<String>
    token: String
}
```

9.3.2 Cloud side payload definitions

9.3.2.1 *CloudResource*

This resource definition differs slightly from Core *Resource* definition. It is used to describe resource on the Cloud side and is used for example to send a registration request to *Registration Handler*. It contains an internal id of the resource on the Cloud side (*internalId*) as well as symbloTe-generated id for the resource (*id*). The internal id is never shared outside of the Cloud side of the symbloTe.

```
CloudResource {  
    internalId:      String  
    id:              String  
    name:            String  
    owner:           String  
    description:     String  
    location:        Location  
    observedProperties: List<String>  
    resourceURL:     String  
    featureOfInterest: String  
    platformId:      String  
}
```

9.3.2.2 *Observation*

This resource definition is used to describe data coming from the platform. It contains, in addition to the observation value itself, the id of the resource queried, together with the location where the observation has been made and the timestamp.

```
Observation {  
    resourceId:      String  
    location:        Location  
    resultTime:      String  
    samplingTime:    String  
    obsValue:        List<ObservationValue>  
}
```

9.4 Description of L1 Integration process

Integration instructions will be described into deliverable “D5.2 – Report on System Integration and Application Development”.

Here some screenshots taken from the online documentation, available on GitHub (<https://github.com/symbiote-h2020/SymbioteCloud/blob/master/README.md>), dated July 13th, 2017.

This is an evolving document, constantly updated according to the software implementation (some screenshot in Figure 8, Figure 9, Figure 10).

Figure 8 – L1 integration process documentation

Figure 9 – L1 integration process documentation

Figure 10 – L1 integration process documentation

9.5 SymbloTe Core – project build, deployment and usage

Build, deployment and usage instructions are described into deliverable “D5.2 – Report on System Integration and Application Development”.